

D1.1 Gender and Ethics Report

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Executive summary

Equal opportunities for women and men within the project has been ensured throughout the project both within each of the partnering companies, across the consortium and among the participating entities in each of the work packages.

Gender issues regarding project outcomes have been evaluated in a public perception study which is presented as part of D6.8.

Ethical principles and the highest standards of research integrity has been guaranteed during the project in agreement with the conditions in the Grant Agreement i.e. as well as applicable international, EU and national law. No ethics issues were identified prior to project execution and none have been identified during project implementation.

1. Introduction

This report is part of the output from Task 1.4 *Management of gender equality, and gender-sensitive research design, ethical and other societal aspects*. This task has been ensuring that all appropriate ethical standards are met and concurrently monitoring project activities for the potential emergence of any areas of concern regarding gender or ethics. The Project coordinator assisted by the Administrative project manager has been monitoring potential issues among the project partners throughout the lifetime of the project.

2. Gender

Gender balance in the project consortium

Table 1. Data reported after the first reporting period (M1-M18) as Gender of researchers and other workforce involved in the project.

Beneficiaries	Number of female researchers	Number of male researchers	Number of females in the workforce other than researchers	Number of males in the workforce other than researchers	Total number of females in the workforce	Total number of males in the workforce
1 – DTI	6	4	5	1	11	5
2 – BANGOR	0	6	1	1	1	7
3 – Innorenew	2	2	1	0	3	2
4 – WSPC	0	3	0	3	0	6
5 – ANECOOP	0	1	1	0	1	1
6 – Tailorzyme	1	1	1	2	2	3
7 – ABP	0	0	16	12	16	12
8 - Emmelev A/S	0	1	2	2	2	3
9 – VERTECH	3	4	4	5	7	9
10 - Franka Marzi	2	2	2	0	4	2
11 – CHIMAR	3	5	0	2	3	7
12 – Innovarum	0	0	6	1	6	1
13 – Jaencoop	2	0	2	3	4	3
14 - MARS GMBH	1	2	1	1	2	3
15 – NATAC	4	4	0	1	4	5
16 - Tate & Lyle	5	4	5	1	10	5
Total	29	39	47	35	76	74

The Pro-Enrich project involves 16 (17) partners from six countries representing research institutes, large industry, SMEs and universities. During the project, partner number 9 Veritech was replaced by partner number 17 Leitac, which reduced the number of participating countries from seven to six. It has been an expressed aim of the project to give equal opportunity to women and men to participate in the project and the project partner group has ensured good gender balance throughout the lifetime of the project. Table 1 shows the balance between women and men in the different roles of the project after the first reporting period (M18). Of

the total reported 150 staff working on the project 29 were female researchers and 39 were male researchers, while the numbers of non-researchers were reported as 47 female employees and 37 male employees in total, which overall gives a close to 50:50 distribution of men and women involved in the project.

The updated numbers for the consortium reported in August 2021 are shown in Table 2. From these numbers it is also apparent that the balance between the genders has been upheld throughout the project with 28 female researchers and 41 male researchers working on the project, while the numbers for non-researchers are 42 and 23 for females and males, respectively.

Table 2. Gender of researchers and non-researchers reported by the consortium in August 2021.

Beneficiaries	Number of female researchers	Number of male researchers	Number of females in the workforce other than researchers	Number of males in the workforce other than researchers	Total number of females in the workforce	Total number of males in the workforce
1 – DTI	6	8	7	1	13	9
2 – BANGOR	0	6	1	1	1	7
3 – Innorenew	3	2	1	1	4	3
4 – WSPC	0	2	0	2	0	4
5 – ANECOOP	0	1	1	2	1	3
6 – Tailorzyme	0	2	3	2	3	4
7 – FBCD	0	0	10	3	10	3
8 – Emmelev A/S	0	1	2	2	2	3
9 - Vertech	-	-	-	-	-	-
10 - Franka Marzi	2	2	2	0	4	2
11 – CHIMAR	3	5	1	2	4	7
12 – Innovarum	0	0	5	0	5	0
13 – Jaencoop	2	0	2	3	4	3
14 - MARS GMBH	1	2	1	1	2	3
15 – NATAC	5	4	1	1	6	5
16 - Tate & Lyle	5	4	5	1	10	5
17 – Leitat	1	2	0	1	1	3
Total	28	41	42	23	70	64

Gender balance in management

The gender distribution of the management team is illustrated in table 3 evidencing that there has been a close to even distribution between men and women.

Table 3. Distribution of women and men in the management team of Pro-Enrich

Role	Female	Male
Coordinator	1	0
Administrative project manager[‡]	1	0
Exploitation manager	0	1
WP leaders – project start (M6)	2*	5
WP leaders – project end (M40)	3*	4

[‡]The Administrative manager assists the coordinator with the day-to-day management of the project.

*including the coordinator leading WP1.

Promotion of gender equality in Pro-Enrich

Equal opportunities for women and men within the project and in the individual teams has been discussed by the steering committee. The consortium policy has recognized the need for flexibility in working arrangements to enable staff to meet personal/family commitments. This has included the opportunity for both men and women to take parental leave during the project. Several partners have had staff members on parental leave during the project including a WP leader at DTI. All involved staff has been given the opportunity to resume their position within the project after return from their leave, while other staff has been committed to maintain the progress of the project during their absence.

Two of the SME partners in the project; Tailorzyme and Innoraum (EURIZON S.L.) have gender imbalance in their staff, however, this does not reflect any gender preferences.

Tailorzyme does not discriminate on the basis of gender, nor race, colour, religion, gender expression, age, national origin, disability, marital status, or sexual orientation for that matter. It is however difficult for a small company with 3 people employed (1 female, 2 males), in addition to the two owners (both male), to address the gender balance at this stage. For future hiring, Tailorzyme will of course pay attention to this.

Innovarum is a consultancy company specialised in the agricultural sector founded by two women in 2013; Maya Hernando and Irene Paredes. Currently, since October of 2019, its team counts with a total of seven people: six women - counting the two founders - and one man. Innovarum strongly believes in equality of opportunities regardless of gender or age. It carries its personnel selection processes based on skills, competences, experience, education and degree of adequacy to the job post requirements of the candidates. Innovarum has selected its current personnel following the conditions above and will continue to do so. However, the present size of the company makes gender imbalances more noticeable. As the company grows, Innovarum will keep on implementing principles for selecting its personnel based on equality of opportunities. Ultimately, this will help even the numbers and build a team well-balanced regarding gender.

Gender issues regarding project outcome

The research and development work in the project has mainly been focused on meeting specific, scientifically defined criteria and therefore it has not been possible to identify any gender related issues regarding this. However, concerning the final products obtained in this project, there is probably a difference in how women and men perceive the outcome of the project, which is most likely more pronounced for products for personal care such as cosmetics compared to for example adhesives for wood. These tendencies have been reviewed during the Public Perception Study which is part of D6.8 Socio-economic repercussions and public perception study. The study shows that the women more than the men show a clear preference for cosmetic products that are perceived as natural and a certain willingness to pay extra for this. On a tendency-level, women are also more also willing to pay extra than men for their cosmetic products.

According to the data received in the public perception study there seems to be good sense in marketing bio-based products specifically to women, because they are more often responsible for household purchases (80% vs. 66% for men), they find sustainability more important when they shop, they find product origin more important, and they care more about products being natural than men. This applies in particular to younger women, as younger generations are more familiar with the concept bio-based than older generations.

Furthermore, we have found that when it comes to gender there is more willingness among women than men to reduce their meat intake. Twice as many women than men do not eat meat, and twice as many men than women have no intentions of changing their diet despite being aware of the climate impact of eating meat. Furthermore, more women than men who still eat meat try to limit their meat intake. This is particularly relevant for the ProEnrich product derived from rapeseed cake (i.e. rapeseed protein extract), which is aiming at providing a plant-based protein alternative for human consumption.

3. Ethics

Ethics in research

The consortium has carried out the work according to the conditions in the Grant Agreement i.e. applying ethical principles (including the highest standards of research integrity) as well as applicable international, EU and national law. All activities have had an exclusive focus on civil applications.

No ethics issues had been identified prior to project execution and none have been identified during project implementation.

All project partners have performed their activities in adherence to the fundamental ethical principles of Horizon 2020 and the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union. The project has not involved the use or exploitation of children or other vulnerable populations, personal data, research on animals or research on Human embryonic stem cells.

All partners adhere to the highest standards of research integrity – as set out, for instance, in the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity – and including, in particular, avoiding fabrication, falsification, plagiarism or other research misconduct and applicable international,

EU and national law. The consortium partners comply with the ethical guidelines as laid down by The National Committees for Research Ethics and the EU guidelines for research projects.

Ethics regarding GDPR

The work on Pro-Enrich has not involved personal data, however an online survey has been performed as part of D6.8. All data has been treated confidentially and according to GDPR guidelines. For more detailed information see the full description of data handling in D6.8.